

Paper 14

A STUDY ON INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY AND ITS IMPACT ON FAMILY MEMEBERS IN PERLA, KASARGOD

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Abstract

This study deal with intellectual disability and its impact on family members in Perla, Kasargod D.T, Kerala. Intellectual disability means different things to different people. It is not a simple phenomenon and the lives of individuals who are retarded can be complicated. An intellectually challenged person is whose mental age develops at a slower rate than normal children and does not achieve full intellectual functions of a normal adult. Intellectual disability generally refers to substantial growth and is manifested in inappropriate or immature reactions to one's environment and below average performance in the academic, psychological, physical and social domains. Accepting such children becomes very difficult to parents, family members and care takers. The objectives of the research are: To identify the effect of intellectual disability on the family; And to find out how psychological, physical, economic and social problems affect the family members of mentally disabled children. The study design used is essentially qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative descriptions are based on some quality or characteristic rather than on some quantity or measured value. Descriptive research design is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that is being studied. This methodology focuses more on the of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject. This study reveals that family members face physical, psychological, economic and social problems.

Keywords: Intellectual disability, Intellectual quotient (IQ), Social, Economic, Psychological, and physiological problems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intellectual disability is one of the mental disabilities caused by mental limited capacity of the person. The abilities like reasoning thinking, planning and adjustment. The limited capacity of the mind makes it difficult to know new things or changes in life. The knowledge, skills and information we receive in life with experience and improving our mistakes. We learn new things from observing and watching others. When people lack the ability to learn from various sources, it will effect on his life and creates problems for leading a happy life. There

are multiple reasons for the intellectual disabilities. Like genetic reasons, brain injuries during birth or after the birth, accidents, medical affect, brain development,

2. CLASSIFICATION OF INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY

The classification given by the American Association of Mental deficiency (1977) is mostly adopted as characterized by subaverage intellectual functioning and impaired adaptive behaviour. The test which was developed by Binet and Simon is used for identification of children with intellectual disability (Termar& Merrill, 1973) which is as follows;

Borderline Intelligence (IQ 83-68): An IQ score that falls in the range from 68-70 to 82-83 suggests that an individual of borderline intelligence. These people are not considered as mentally retarded as they do not have impairments in their independent living skills. They are identified by the teachers or educators and slow learners.

Mild Intellectual disability (IQ 67-52): Mild mentally retarded people are indistinguishable from the general population, but they are unable to profit to any great degree from the programme of the regular schools. They are also called as educable mentally retarded having the following potentials of development.

Moderate Intellectual disability (IQ 51-36): The moderately mentally retarded individual is unable to profit from the normal school programme. They are also known as 'Trainable mentally retarded'.

Severe Intellectual disability (IQ 35-20):The severely mentally retarded people may have associate handicaps such as motor problems or significant speech and language deficits. Special school programmes will emphasis basic developmental skills, communication and adaptive behaviour. People who have severe intellectual disability can work in supervised settings.

Profound Intellectual disability (IQ< 20): Individuals under this category require custodial care at the upper limit of this range and life sustaining maintenance at the lower levels. They need care and help at all levels.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jani (1967) indicated that parental feelings were marked by anxiety about future. Also, negative effects towards other siblings, psychological stress, decreased interaction with neighbours and relatives, misunderstandings within family and economic loss were significant factors associated with presence of a child with intellectual disability in the family. Sambhu Upadhyay and Anju Singh (2009) conducted a study to find the impact of level of intellectual disability of children on the perception of psychosocial problems and needs by parents of intellectual disability children in providing care to them. The study was conducted on a purposive sample of 100 parents of intellectually disabled children. Parents of moderately retarded children registered more problems in all aspects compared with parents having mildly retarded children. The needs expressed by the parents of mildly retarded child were more of preventive and adjustment nature whereas parents of moderately retarded children were more concerned with lifelong adjustment and financial security including government help of their child.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Objectives provide direction to the study. On the basis of objectives investigator chooses the areas of data collection, respondents and systematic analysis. The objectives of the research study are; to identify the effect of intellectual disability on the family; to find out how psychological, physical, economic and social problems affect the family members of mentally disabled children.

5. METHODOLOGY

The study design used is essentially qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative descriptions are based on some quality or characteristic rather than on some quantity or measured value. Descriptive research design is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that is being studied. This methodology focuses more on the of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject. The research aims at describing the psycho-social, physical and economic problems of family members of intellectually disabled children. SPSS is used for data analysis and interpretation.

6. MAJOR FINDINGS

This study reveals that the family members of intellectually disabled children have psycho-social, physical and economic problems.

Psychological Problems

Psychological problems	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Blame	49 (98%)	0	1(2%)	0
Upset	41 (82%)	1 (2%)	8 (16%)	0
Limit growth	10(20%)	17 (34%)	23 (46%)	0
Emotional conflicts	38 (78%)	2 (4%)	9 (18%)	0

The above table shows the psychological problems of the respondents. Blame: 98 percent said that they don't blame anybody and 2 percent said that sometimes they blame others for the intellectual disability of child. Upset: 82 percent said that they are not at all upset 16 percent are sometimes upset about it and 2 percent are upset about intellectual disability of the child. Limit growth: 46 percent expressed that intellectual disability of the child sometimes limit the growth of the respondents. 34 percent said that it always limits the growth and 20 percent said not at all limit the growth. Emotional Conflict: 78 percent told

that there is no emotional conflict, 18 percent expressed sometimes there is emotional conflict and 4 percent said there is emotional conflict. From this table it is clear that the majority of the respondents do have psychological problems due to the intellectual disability of the child

Physical Problems

Physical problem	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Physical burden	21 (42%)	8 (16%)	21 (42%)	0
Need help	17 (34%)	19 (38%)	12 (24%)	2 (4%)
Physical strain	17 (34%)	9 (18%)	23 (46%)	1 (2%)

The table depicts the physical strain. Physical burden, need for help and physical strain. *Physical burden:* 42 percent said they have physical burden always and sometimes respectively and 8 percent said that they have physical problem. *Need some help:* 38 percent of respondent said that they need some help to take care the child, 34 percent said no need help 24 said occasionally they need help and 4 percent often they need help. *Physical strain:* 46 percent of respondents expressed that they have sometimes physical strain, 34 percent said they have no physical problems, 18 percent said that often they have physical strain. From the above explanation it is clear that majority of the respondents have physical problems because they need to help children physically such as carry the child and assisting them for their personal needs.

Social Problems

Social problem	Shame	Inferiority	Anger	No feeling
Going for social gathering with the child	0	0	1 (2%)	49 (98%)
Reaction to the comment	25 (50%)	10 (20%)	3 (6%)	12 (24%)
Feeling before friends	1 (2%)	13 (26%)	NO	31 (72%)
Feeling inferiority	1 (2%)	36 (72%)	13 (26%)	0
Child is problem to the family	30 (60%)	1 (2%)	19 (38%)	0
Social Stress	15 (30%)	11 (22%)	24 (48%)	0

The above table explains about different social problems, that the respondents have and they are following. *Going for social gathering with the child:* 98 percent said that they have no feeling and 2 percent said they have anger when people ask about the child. *Reaction to the comment:* 50 percent said that they have shame, 24 percent said they have no feeling at all.

20 percent they have inferiority complex and 6 percent have anger. *Feeling before friends*: 72 percent have no feelings to take the child anywhere as they go for gatherings, 26 percent have inferiority feelings and 2 percent have shame. From above table it is clear that all the respondents face certain degree of social problems. *Feeling inferiority*: 76 percent respondents said that they have inferiority feeling, 26 percent said sometimes and 2 percent said they have no inferiority at all. *Child is problem to the family*: The majority 60 percent said no child is not a problem to the family, 38 percent said child is sometimes problem to the family and 2 percent said child is problem to the family. *Social stress*: The majority 48 percent of the respondents said that they have sometimes social stress, 30 percent have not at all and 22 percent said they have social stress.

Economic Problems

Economic problem	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Spend money for education and training	30 (60%)	2 (4%)	18 (36%)	0
Financial burden on treatment	7 (14%)	14 (28%)	29 (58%)	0
Financial burden on the maintenance of the family	12 (24%)	14 (28%)	23 (46%)	1 (2%)

The above table shows the economic problems of the respondents. Following are the main economic problems. *Spending money for the education and training*: 60 percent said they do not spend money for the training and education, 36 percent said they spend sometimes and 4 percent said they spend money for training and education of the children. *Financial burden on the treatment*: 58 percent have expressed that they face economic burden sometimes for the treatment, 28 percent said they have always financial problem and 14 percent said that they don't have economic problem for the treatment of the child. *Economic burden on the maintenance of the family*: 46 percent of respondents viewed that they have sometimes burden on the maintenance of the family, 28 percent totally agreed that they have burden on and 24 percent said they have no burden and 2 percent said that they have often burden on the maintenance of the family. It is clear that majority of the respondents have economic problem due to the child's intellectual disability. They cannot go for the work someone need to take care the child and there are expenses like treatment, education and training of the child. From the above analysis we can conclude that the family members of the intellectually disabled children face physical, psychological, economic and social problems.

7. SUGGESTION

- Respondents have social stigma and social isolation attached to intellectual disability, and it is mainly due to minimum education. Therefore, it is necessary to provide psycho-social education to the families of intellectually disabled children.
- Government can provide education and trainings to the intellectually disabled children, thus can establish special school in that area.

- Government can appoint social workers in the panchayath level to supervise and provide different supports to the families of intellectually disabled children and especially psycho-social support.

8. CONCLUSION

Here the investigator sums up the study on intellectual disability and its impact on family. And this study was conducted in Perla, Kasargod district in Kerala state. Intellectual disability has lot of impact on family members specially those who take care of the intellectually disabled children. The major concern of the investigator is to study intellectual disability and its impact on family members and how this impact can affect family at large. This study leaves behind scope to further study on problems of disabled children and how those children are affected by the problems of family members. Disability has affected family members personal life and professional life. Other important areas of focus are on different services and help that can be provided for the wellbeing of disabled children as well as their family at large.

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